

Spectrophotometric Determination of Pyrimidinethiols with Selenium

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Pyrimidinethiols are vulcanisation accelerators¹, and possess bactericidal activity. Only a few methods are reported for the determination of pyrimidine-thiols² and most of them are indirect, time-consuming and less sensitive. Here we present a simple, direct, rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of 1-phenyl-4,4,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol (1), 1-(4'-tolyl)-4,4,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol (2) and 1-(4'-aminobenzoyl)-4,4,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol (3) based on the extraction of their selenium complexes into carbon tetrachloride.

(1)

(2) R = -CH₃
(3) R = -COOH

Results and Discussion

Maximum absorbance was obtained when pH of the aqueous phase was 9.7–10.0, and 2.0–2.5 ml of 2% sodium selenite was used. The complexes were extractable into chloroform, benzene, ethyl acetate, isobutyl methyl ketone, amyl acetate, dichloromethane and diethyl ether. Maximum ab-

sorbance was obtained with carbon tetrachloride and hence it was used in this method. The calibration graphs obtained under the optimum condition were linear over wide concentration range (Table 1). The molar absorptivity and the relative standard deviation for ten replicate determinations of 200 µg of pyrimidinethiols are also given in Table 1.

Sample solutions containing 200 µg of pyrimidinethiols and various amounts of different anions (as alkali metal salt) or metal ions were prepared and the general procedure was applied. The following foreign ions in the mg amounts (shown in parentheses) did not interfere: acetate (19), bromide (16), chloride (142), citrate (12), sulphate (18), thiosulphate (23), metabisulphite (29), ortho-phosphate (67), thiocyanate (29), tartrate (29), EDTA (186), Pb^{II} (1.0), Zn^{II} (0.4), Bi^{III} (1.25), Ni^{II} (0.9), V^V (0.2), Th^{IV} (1.4), Mo^{VI} (0.5) and Mn^{II} (0.3). Copper (0.6) can be masked with EDTA (100 mg).

The method is fairly selective, sensitive, rapid and can be recommended for the determination of pyrimidinethiols.

Experimental

A digital pH meter and a SP spectronic 20 spectrophotometer were used. A 2% sodium selenite solution was prepared in distilled water. Pyrimidinethiols were prepared by the reported method³ and purified by crystallisation. Stock solutions of pyrimidinethiols were prepared in

TABLE I—ABSORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF SELENIUM PYRIMIDINETHIOL COMPLEXES

Compd.	Effective concn. range $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Relative standard deviation (%)
1-Phenyl-4,4,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol	5–120	3.619	0.84
1-(4'-Tolyl)-4,4,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol	5–32	1.46	1.3
1-(4'-Aminobenzoic)-4,4,6-trimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol	5–70	1.795	0.78

dimethylformamide and further diluted as desired. Boric acid buffer was prepared by mixing equal volumes of boric acid and KCl solutions (each 0.2 M) and pH adjusted to 9.8 with NaOH (0.2 M).

Procedure : To a known volume (≤ 1 ml) of the sample containing 200 μg of the pyrimidinethiol, 2% sodium selenite solution (2.5 ml) and boric acid buffer (pH 9.8; 1.0 ml) were added. The contents were diluted to 5 ml with distilled water and allowed to stand for 2 min. The solution was then transferred into a dry tube containing anhydrous sodium

sulphate (1 g). A second extract obtained with another 5 ml of carbon tetrachloride had negligible absorbance, so the absorbance of the first extract measured at 400 nm for pyrimidinethiols **1** and **2**, and that at 390 nm for **3** against a reagent blank, were used for determination.

References

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